

Caiques can become very bonded to their owners, often displaying excitement when they see them. They are highly intelligent parrots and can be taught to perform tricks and respond to commands. They love to explore and play, and will often be seen climbing around their cage and chewing on items. They like to show off to their owners and will often need plenty of toys and activities to [caique parrots](#) keep them entertained. They have powerful beaks and like to chew, so sturdy toys and items should be provided to prevent accidental damage. Caiques also appreciate treats like nuts and fruits and need a variety of fresh foods in their diet to keep them healthy and vital.